

Critical factors on the implementation of school programs

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Abstract

Understanding the critical factors that affect successful program implementation enables a comprehensive examination of the conditions that support or impede school targets and goals, directing the development of focused interventions and research-based strategies to improve program sustainability and effectiveness. Through an online survey utilizing the select box ranking approach, perceptions on how school heads rank various facilitating and hindering factors influencing the implementation of school programs were determined. Items in the survey were derived from the review of related studies and submitted Program Implementation Review Reports of school heads in the Department of Education, City Schools Division of Bacoor in the calendar year 2023 and were validated using the Fleiss Kappa Index and Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio. It was found out that alignment and adaptability of programs to the school's context is perceived as the leading contributory factor in the successful implementation of school programs while time constraints and conflict of schedules are perceived as the leading contributory factors in the unsuccessful implementation of school programs. Through the Kruskal-Wallis test, it was also found out that factors such as sex, number of years serving as school head, educational attainment, and level of school handled have no influence on how the implementation of school programs may be perceived. Following the identification and analysis of both facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation of school programs, a technical assistance plan was developed to address identified challenges and optimize program implementation.

Keywords: School Programs; Implementation; Facilitating Factors; Hindering Factors

1. Introduction

Education is the foundation of progress. It is an avenue to empower individuals to become active agents of positive change and collectively address pressing societal challenges. By investing in education, societies can build a solid foundation for intergenerational sustainability, cultural sensitivity, and pacific prosperity. It is on this premise that the Department of Education (DepEd) manages to promote access, quality, and equity in the Philippine Basic Education System through various programs offered in schools. Under Republic Act No. 9155 or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, all units across governance levels have roles and responsibilities in the implementation of school programs as an educational service and commitment. Implementing school programs is a complex process that involves both internal and external stakeholders such as school heads, teachers, learners, parents, policymakers, and other community members. Aside from equipping learners with the necessary knowledge, skills, and values for them to become productive citizens of the country, school programs help in providing opportunities for professional development of teaching and non-teaching personnel, prompting collaboration among members of the community, sharing of best practices between individual and collective schools, and empowering schools on management decisions like fiscal autonomy. The DepEd oversees developing, planning, implementing, and coordinating programs in formal and non-formal education at the elementary and secondary levels. Some programs implemented on a national scale are the Brigada Eskwela, School-based Feeding, Every Child a Reader, and Adopt a School. Locally, division offices and schools implement programs according to their unique backgrounds and contexts.

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One critical factor in the implementation of school programs is effective leadership. School heads are vital in providing clear directions, allocating resources, and monitoring progress to ensure the program is implemented as intended (Hallinger & Heck, 2011). Effective leadership involves building a shared vision, creating a positive school culture, and fostering teacher collaboration. Good leaders set a clear vision and values to nurture the culture of their school and are actively and visibly involved in school programs to ensure their success. They foster relationships between school staff, teachers, and students to create a safe and collaborative learning environment. Another critical factor is teacher involvement. Teachers are the frontline implementers of school programs, and their involvement in the program's development and implementation is crucial (Hallinger & Heck, 2011). They are important as their knowledge and experience can inform program design. However, teachers need to understand a program's goals and objectives, and how it aligns with the curriculum. They also need to be provided with adequate training and resources to implement the program effectively (Guskey & Yoon, 2009). Parental involvement is also a critical factor in the successful implementation of school programs as they can provide valuable insights and feedback on the program's implementation (Epstein, 2011). In addition, when parents are involved in the implementation of school programs, learners' motivation and academic performance are enhanced (Henderson & Mapp, 2002).

Other critical factors that may influence the successful implementation of school programs include adequate funding, community support, effective communication, and program evaluation (Fullan, 2011). Adequate funding is crucial for the successful implementation of school programs. It ensures that resources are available to support the program's implementation, including training materials and equipment. On the other hand, community support enhances activities that require all stakeholders to offer full engagement in meeting learner needs. Meanwhile, effective communication involves conveying expectations, goals, and the value of a program to all stakeholders in a clear, concise, and timely manner. Regular communication between decision-makers, heads, and teaching and non-teaching personnel can ensure that everyone is on the same page and headed toward the achievement of the same objectives.

School programs must target positive reform in the education system despite challenges in the learning landscape of the country. To ensure that school programs are geared towards the achievement of its set goals, the DepEd established the Basic Education Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (BEMEF) through DepEd Order No. 29 series of 2022. It sets the performance measure in which units across governance levels must operate, tracks the achievement of school programs with regards to its planning and budget strategies, and strengthens evidence-based practices for decision-making, policy formulation, and program adjustment. The BEMEF stipulates guidelines for the conduct of the Program Implementation Review (PIR), a quarterly mechanism that tracks the completion of activities, usage of funds, and fulfillment of outcomes in each school program. The PIR provides valuable insights into how school programs may be improved to ensure that they meet their intended goals and objectives.

As mentioned earlier, the success of implementing school programs depends on numerous critical factors. The purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation of school programs in the Department of Education, City Schools Division of Bacoor. This study will provide inputs for the development of a technical assistance plan for school heads and other stakeholders involved in the implementation of school programs. Educators must have a thorough understanding of the goals of a program as well as the best practices for its implementation. With this information, educators will be better equipped to comprehend their existing programs implemented and enhance future services to ultimately provide improved services to learners and other stakeholders.

2. Literature Review

This section presents a brief discussion of literature and studies from local and foreign sources reviewed by the researcher, which further enriched the concept of the study and helped in describing the research design to guide the conduct of this research. The summary of findings for each source is arranged chronologically based on its publication date.

Berkel, Mauricio, Schoenfelder, & Sandler (2011) proposed an integrated theoretical model with pathways from dimensions such as fidelity, quality of delivery, program adaptation, and participant responsiveness to program outcomes. Fidelity is the adherence to the program curriculum. It may alternatively be described as the degree to which program components that were mandated were provided in accordance with program protocol. There are no commonly recognized criteria of measurement for fidelity, even though it is typically operationalized as a percentage of the manualized information given or the amount of time devoted to each of the essential components. Measuring fidelity should involve either determining the essential elements of the manualized material and evaluating if they were supplied, or determining how much time was spent on each essential element. On the other hand, quality of delivery is the proficiency with which facilitators convey information and engage participants. It refers to the teaching and clinical skill with which the program is implemented. It might also be described as the procedures utilized to provide

participants with program material, such as the interactive teaching techniques employed by facilitators. By encouraging collaboration and involving students in the learning process, interactive teaching develops participant competency to apply program skills successfully. Another crucial component of the quality of delivery is the excitement and clarity with which program facilitators convey the material. Activities that foster a secure and encouraging atmosphere that promotes involvement and speeds up learning include summarizing and reflective listening. Promoting unity among participants is another crucial aspect of quality for group-delivered preventative interventions. Program adaptations are modifications and additions made especially in content of the program during implementation. Adaptation, sometimes called reinvention, modification, or proficiency, refers to the degree to which facilitators add to or change methods and content that are outlined in the handbook. It may be a concern that program effectiveness will be diminished by facilitator adaptation. Nonetheless, the unfavorable perception of facilitator adaptability is probably brought to by the common accusation that it lacks authenticity. Adaptability is better described as program additions than as a departure from fidelity. By doing this, it becomes easy to distinguish between an incapacity to carry out the program as intended and what might be a facilitator contribution to the curriculum, based on the close understanding of the local community. Meanwhile, participant responsiveness is the participants' level of interest in and involvement in each program. It is described as excitement and participation levels as a crucial element of execution. Using metrics including the number of sessions attended, active involvement, satisfaction, and completion of home practice, responsiveness may be operationalized.

Each of the aforementioned factors has been shown to have an impact on program results and serves as a possible source of variation from the program as intended. In this model, several specific hypotheses are specified which are (1) both quality and participant responsiveness moderate the effect of fidelity, (2) participant responsiveness mediates quality of outcomes, and (3) by responsiveness, adaptability influences participant outcomes directly and indirectly. Program implementation is seen as multidimensional which emphasizes the importance of facilitator and participant behaviors in achieving program outcomes. Both dimensions are interdependent yet may influence outcomes in different ways. On the other hand, a working taxonomy of eight implementation outcomes was proposed by Proctor, Silmere, Raghavan, Hovmand, Aarons, Bunger, & Hensley (2011). These implementation outcomes may be measured in terms of attitudes, intentions, and observed behaviors. First is acceptability or the perception that a specific treatment, service, practice, or innovation is agreeable, palatable, or satisfactory among implementation stakeholders. Next is adoption or the purpose, initial choice, or action to test out or use a new idea or an evidence-based practice. Next is appropriateness or the perception of the innovations or evidence-based practice's fit, relevance, or compatibility for a certain practice context, provider, or customer. Next is the cost or the financial impact of a project's implementation. Fifth is the feasibility or the ability of a novel procedure or innovation to be successfully implemented within a specific organization or location. Next is fidelity or the degree to which an intervention was carried out by the original protocol's instructions. Next is penetration or the integration of a practice into a service environment and its supporting systems. Last is sustainability or the degree to which a newly introduced treatment is maintained or institutionalized within a service setting's continuous, consistent operations. Tracking the progress of program implementation may be organized through the proposed taxonomy of implementation outcomes. It may define mechanisms and causal links for successful implementation.

Fullan (2011) introduced 'drivers' that lever policies and strategies for the successful implementation of school programs. Right drivers include capacity building, group work, instruction, and systemic solutions. These are effective because they concentrate directly on changing the culture of school systems such as norms, values, skills, practices, and relationships. They also encourage teachers' and learners' internal motivation, enhancing continuous improvement in instruction, motivating group or team effort, and inspiring all educators and learners. In contrast, there are 'wrong drivers' that modify the structure, processes, and the system's formal properties without achieving the internal core of the implementation. This includes (1) using accountability like test results and teacher appraisal to reward or punish teachers, (2) promoting individual quality instead of group solutions, (3) reliance on technology in carrying out instruction, and (4) utilizing fragmented rather than systemic strategies. Placing teachers and learners as the main driving force is essential for system-wide success. This entails coordinating the program's objectives with individuals' innate drives for change. Getting something done well that matters to you and the people you are working with gives you intrinsic energy. Being successful at a task that is personally meaningful and contributes to others as well as society motivates most people after their basic requirements are addressed. Personal contributions are more fulfilling when they are part of a team effort merging personal and social goals. Implementation of school programs cannot come from policies and techniques that do not promote such high intrinsic motivation throughout the entire system. Moreover, initiatives that do not result in enhanced capability are similarly doomed to failure.

Duerden & Witt (2012) emphasized that the identification of successful programs and practices can be facilitated by the combination of implementation evaluations and outcome evaluations. The spread of evidence-based programs is encouraged by this information, which also offers guidance on how to implement programs and create the desired

results. A greater emphasis on integrated assessments that address both implementation and outcomes would be extremely beneficial for educators. Quality implementation evaluations may lead to (1) improved validity of the program results, (2) a better understanding of how programs are carried out, (3) greater comprehension of program results, (4) improved best practices dissemination, and (5) more chances to improve programs in an informed manner. The idea of program integrity is the extent to which a program is carried out as originally intended. Its five main dimensions are adherence, dosage, quality of delivery, participant responsiveness, and program differentiation. Adherence is the degree to which program execution meets operational expectations. Dosage refers to the quantity of a service that a participant receives. Quality of Delivery relates to how the service was delivered. Participant responsiveness gauges people's participation and engagement in the program. Program differentiation entails the identification of program elements to determine how specifically they contribute to the results. They proposed a sample implementation evaluation strategy that may be applied to each dimension. In adherence, the evaluation component is the use of curriculum during mentoring sessions while the observation method may be the observations of mentoring sessions and session logs completed by adult mentors. For dosage, the evaluation component is the number of mentoring sessions while the observation method may be session logs. For the quality of delivery, the evaluation component is the quality of curriculum delivery and the observation method may be observations of mentoring sessions and survey questions about the program. Lastly, for participant responsiveness, the evaluation component may be engaged in the mentoring process, and the observation method may be interviews and surveys with satisfaction and engagement questions.

Durlak (2013) stated that success is feasible even though numerous factors might influence the quality of the implementation process. The processes for implementing a school program may appear straightforward: identify a need, hire staff, and supply the service. Yet, effective program implementation necessitates thorough planning in advance, the involvement of numerous stakeholders, and a procedure that ensures accountability. Poorly administered programs not only lower the likelihood of helping learners in need but also waste limited finances because they are unlikely to be particularly successful. In addition, when software is implemented improperly, we don't know whether it works. He identified twenty-three (23) factors that affect program implementation. For societal factors, he listed (1) scientific theory and research, (2) political pressures and influences, (3) availability of funding, and (4) local, state, or federal policies. For educator characteristics, he mentioned the (5) perceived need for the program, (6), perceived benefits of the program, (7) self-efficacy, and (8) skill proficiency. Meanwhile, for the characteristics of the program, he listed (9) compatibility with the local setting and (10) adaptability. He also included the factors related to the organization hosting the program which is (11) positive work climate, (12) openness to innovation, (13) integration of new programming, (14) shared vision, (15) shared decision-making, (16) coordination with other agencies, (17) openness of communication, (18) formulation of tasks, (19) effective leadership, (20) program champion, and (21) managerial support. Lastly, he stipulated the factors specific to the implementation process which are (22) successful training and (23) ongoing technical assistance. He also proposed four phases involving quality program implementation which include (1) initial considerations regarding the host setting, (2) creating a structure for implementation, (3) ongoing structure once implementation begins, and (4) improving future applications. He also emphasized that evaluations of well-executed initiatives should serve as the foundation for judgments about public policy. Alternative programs' relative worth and cost-effectiveness cannot be assessed in any other case. Many stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, local practitioners, and local administrators, are jointly responsible for high-quality implementation. The better the implementation, the more likely it is that the program will provide the desired results.

Palestina, Pangan, and Ancho (2020) reiterated that the implementation of school programs plays a crucial part in curriculum development because it intentionally fosters educational innovations to overcome change on an acknowledged issue in the educational system. They added that to achieve an educational reform that would represent both educational traditions and newly mandated curriculum policies, curriculum design capabilities, learning content expertise, and political capital must be leveraged to their utmost potential. This makes the multifaceted layer of involvement of curriculum implementers and educational designers extremely important. Anchored on Ecological System Theory (EST) by Bronfenbrenner (1979), they noted that the commitment of teachers serves as the major facilitating factor in successful program implementation. On the other hand, teacher workloads need to be addressed seriously since they skew students' perceptions of how well programs are being implemented. Leaders in the education sector can align programs and policies based on classroom experiences and practices as well as research-based inputs by carefully examining the facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation processes of curricula. Carillo & Janer (2022) ascertained that quality learning outcomes through different school programs will be better achieved when working conditions for teachers are altered and their educational repertoire is expanded. The level of teachers' involvement in school activities is a key indicator of how well the school is run. The institutional goals of the school can only be met if teachers participate in a sustained, positive, and long-term manner. Upholding democratic norms at school is demonstrated by involvement and effective engagement. The main difficulties that teachers face when participating in school programs are excessive paperwork and long working hours, improper distribution of program

memos, teachers' lack of understanding of how the program is implemented, lack of opportunities for teachers to demonstrate their skills and talents, and a lack of support for creating an environment that fosters learning. In addition to teaching obligations, teachers are required to "diligently perform tasks connected with their job and the basic functions of the school. Teachers interact with information, communicate with numerous entities, confer with them, and engage in negotiation as part of carrying out those jobs. In addition to the aforementioned duties, school administrators often expect teachers to carry out several administrative, organizational, and other tasks.

Chatzipanagiotou & Katsarou (2023) asserted that modern school leadership has long been regarded as one of the most crucial elements contributing to school effectiveness as well as a catalyst for change and strategic innovation, entailing the creation of a compelling vision, corresponding goals, and an appropriate plan for implementation, monitoring, and review. However, the recent COVID-19 pandemic global outbreak's disruption of the delivery of educational services exposed flaws in school leadership theory that was primarily related to the failure of most school principals to adopt the necessary crisis management techniques to quickly adjust to a new reality and successfully confront impending challenges, at both the instructional and organizational levels. A significant lack of infrastructure and technological equipment at the school level that undermined learning continuity and the caliber of distance learning during the pandemic; a lack of sufficient funding resources that prevented the materialization of a school crisis management plan as evidenced by material deficiencies and shortages in human resource; and a lack of a strong crisis plan that exposed school leaks; are just a few of the challenges in implementing school programs during the pandemic. They stated that school leaders valued distributed and collaborative leadership styles equally in practice during the pandemic period, allowing them to effectively plan their responsive strategy, instilling a sense of shared responsibility to others within the school through a delegation of duties, and emphasizing the collegial network and a sense of belongingness aimed at the adoption of a collective crisis leadership response. Villanueva & Buenbrazo (2023) supported the earlier claims by stating that to achieve the government's objective of delivering high-quality basic education, school administrators play a crucial role in adapting to changes in the educational system such as during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Republic Act 9155, also known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, the school head oversees both the administrative and academic operations of a school or group of schools. Administration of instructional programs, staff management, human resource management, financial and physical resource management, stakeholder relationship management, and upkeep of a supportive environment that fosters safety and security for both students and teachers are all duties of school administrators. School administrators have a significant impact on educational policy, particularly when it comes to motivating teachers and enhancing the educational environment. The composition of educational power, management challenges, and new learning trends have all been identified by school administrators as key problems. On the other hand, the correct mindset, attitudes toward people, and drive to increase performance and productivity are the foundation of effective leadership. In the new normal of education, additional roles of school administrators are to ensure adherence of school facilities to health protocols, manage teachers in their performance of responsibilities amid the new work scheme, and maintain quality of education despite threats to authenticity in learners' academic performance.

Due to the changes brought about by the pandemic and the rapidly changing world in general, Vidal (2023) proposed the "Systems Thinking" approach to be used in school leadership. Systems thinking is a strategy to analyze complicated events and problems and come up with solutions. Instead of analyzing each component independently, it requires looking at how various system components interact with one another and function. Many aspects of education have used systems thinking, such as curriculum development, teacher professional development, and school leadership. Systems Thinking aids educators in comprehending and addressing the intricate and linked structure of educational systems. It entails considering the connections and interactions among various system components, including laws, funding, educational institutions, faculty, supplies, and learners. Teachers, administrators, and policymakers redesigning educational systems or institutions can all use this strategy in education. By understanding how various systems interact, systems thinking can also engage students in the learning process and aid in the development of critical thinking abilities. The use of systems thinking in education has the potential to be a successful approach to today's problems. On several levels, it can improve decision-making, foster resiliency, and support adaptive transformation. Education leaders and practitioners can decide whether to use systems thinking by carefully weighing its possible advantages and drawbacks. This could entail providing chances for cross-sector collaboration and co-creation of solutions, as well as strengthening educators' and education leaders' ability for systems thinking. Because of this, systems thinking in education has significant potential advantages and warrants further study. By adopting this strategy and acquiring the required abilities, educators can more effectively traverse the difficulties of the modern world and produce more egalitarian, resilient, and flexible educational systems.

In a comprehensive literature review by Shen & Joseph (2021), the complex relationship of sex and leadership was discussed. It was pointed out that sex variances in leader effectiveness and leadership skills are insignificant. However, sex variances in leadership behaviors favor female leaders and interpersonal processes are biased against women. Sex

may also affect intrapersonal processes due to risk tolerance. Similarly, Dwiri & Okatan (2021) found out differences between male and female leadership and its influence on decision making and employees relationships wherein female leaders are said to be more effective and have a huge impact than male leaders on decision making and employees relationships. In terms of leadership experience, Fresh Essays (2022) differentiated elderly leaders between young leaders in terms of their attributes, competences, and experience. Elderly learners are characterized as those with wisdom, loyalty, and firmness in making sound and excellent decisions. They are perceived to be knowledgeable and skillful as they can forecast results of their decisions because of their experience. On the other hand, young leaders are characterized as courageous, bold, competitive, and outstanding in their work for having fresh ideas, practical approaches, and functional trends. They are perceived as innovative in monitoring and evaluating performance of their subordinates. With the abundant characterizations of elderly and young leaders, Hait (2020) discussed that stereotypes on age differences may result to poor behaviors, low performance, decreased self-efficacy, and conflict among members of the organization. He reiterated that there are no substantial differences on leadership styles as defined by ages and perceptions placed on such is a concern to organizations. He added that the perceptions may be changed through positive organizational practices like honest conversations, shared experiences, mentoring, and coaching. Meanwhile, Jackson (2020) stated that educational attainment has a significant relationship to leadership styles. Using a quantitative research design, he identified that personality and motivation of leaders improve as the educational attainment of leaders also increase. These results support an earlier study conducted by Kotur & Anbazhagan (2014) which state that increase on the educational attainment of leaders is positively associated with the democratic leadership style that they exhibit in the organization. Decrease on education attainment of leaders will result on manifestation of autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles which are both recognized as less effective approaches in management of an organization.

Findings of both local and international studies cited show that various facilitating factors may be used as strategies in the successful implementation of school programs, and when hindering factors are not addressed, the results would be otherwise. Although the studies have provided insights on the influence of sex, number of years serving as school head, and educational attainment on the implementation of school programs, the effect of level of school handled (Elementary, Junior High, and Senior High) has not been clarified or elucidated yet in previously conducted studies, highlighting the need for further research. The findings and gaps in related literature presented provide the basis for the conduct of this present study, which emphasizes the extent to which facilitating and hindering factors are perceived and experienced by the respondents in the context of the implementation of their school programs.

3. Conceptual Framework

Understanding the facilitating and hindering factors that affect successful program implementation enables a comprehensive examination of the conditions that support or impede school targets and goals, directing the development of focused interventions and research-based strategies to improve program sustainability and effectiveness. Following the identification and analysis of both facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation of school programs, a technical assistance plan will be developed to address identified challenges and optimize program implementation. The figure below shows the conceptual framework of this study.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework of the Study

3.1. Research Questions

This study aimed to identify the critical factors on implementation of school programs in the City Schools Division of Bacoor. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

- What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Sex (Male or Female)
 - Number of Years Serving as School Head
 - Educational Attainment
 - Level of School Handled (Elementary, Junior High School, Senior High School)
- How do respondents rank the given facilitating and hindering factors in terms of contribution to the implementation of school programs?
- How do perceptions on facilitating and hindering factors differ when grouped according to respondents' profile?
- What technical assistance plan for school heads can be developed based on the findings?

3.2. Scope and Limitation

This study focused on the critical factors for the implementation of school programs in the City Schools Division of Bacoor in the calendar year 2023. Data were collected from forty-three purposefully selected school heads from public elementary, junior high, and senior high schools in the said division. The goal of this study was to examine the elements that influence the implementation of school programs in the Department of Education, City Schools Division of Bacoor. This study did not cover the implementation of school programs in previous calendar years. Each of the respondents was given the same questionnaire that served as the main source of data. Findings of this study helped in the creation of a technical assistance plan for school heads in the successful implementation of school programs.

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Sampling

The convenience sampling method was utilized in selecting the forty-three (43) school heads in the Department of Education, City Schools Division of Bacoor who served as respondents in this study. According to Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim (2016), convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling method that has limitations due to its subjective nature but is useful when the researcher has limited time, resources, and workforce or does not intend to create generalizations for the whole population. Members of the target population who meet certain practical criteria, such as easy accessibility, geographic proximity, availability at a specific time, or a willingness to participate, are included for the study's purposes through convenience sampling. It can also apply to demographic research subjects that are simple for a researcher to obtain.

4.2. Data Collection

Data were collected using an online survey application. Items in the survey questionnaire were derived from the review of related studies and submitted Program Implementation Review Reports of school heads in the Department of Education, City Schools Division of Bacoor in the calendar year 2023. It is composed of three parts. First is the introduction, which contains the rationale of the study and the consent to participate in the study. Second is the respondent's profile, which includes their sex (male or female), number of years serving as school head, educational attainment, and level of school handled (elementary, junior high, senior high school). The third part contains questions on the facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation of school programs. The online survey utilized the Select Box Ranking Approach, which allowed the respondents to shift the options up and down until they were in an order that represented their preference.

The face validity of the instrument was determined using the Fleiss' Kappa. Fleiss' Kappa measures the agreement between three or more raters when data is either close-ended, ordinal, or nominal. It ranges from 0 to 1, wherein 0 indicates no agreement and 1 indicates perfect agreement (Falotico & Quatto, 2015). Table 1 shows the rating of five (5) validators on the given items under two (2) categories, namely (a) Facilitating Factors in Implementation of School Programs and (b) Hindering Factors in Implementation of School Programs, in which the former obtained a rating of perfect agreement and only fair agreement for the latter.

Table 1 Overall Fleiss Kappa Rating of Items in Facilitating and Hindering Factors in the Implementation of School Programs

Facilitating Factors	Rating					TOTAL	
						Yes (1)	No (0)
Collaboration and harmonious relationship among teaching and non-teaching personnel.	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Effective leadership and monitoring by the school head	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Teachers' high commitment and dedication	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Stakeholders' active involvement, responsibility, and accountability	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Open, constant, and transparent communication channels	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Alignment and adaptability of the program to the school's context and needs	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Provision of technical assistance by division personnel	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Utilization of research-based and data-driven practices	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Integration of technology across various aspects of program implementation	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
<i>p</i> =						45	0
Hindering Factors	Rating					TOTAL	
						Yes (1)	No (0)
Unforeseen weather /calamity disturbances resulting to changes in learning modalities	0	1	1	1	1	4	1
Implementation of the "No Disruption of Classes" policy	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Requires sufficient funding, materials, technology, and space in the school premises	0	1	1	1	1	4	1
Lack of understanding on program implementation, monitoring, and evaluation	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Low commitment and dedication of teachers	1	1	0	0	1	3	2
Low stakeholders' support	1	1	0	0	1	3	2
Numerous teacher workloads and lack of manpower	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
Poor coordination between teaching and non-teaching personnel	1	1	0	0	1	3	2
Time constraints and conflicting schedule of activities	1	1	1	1	1	5	0
<i>p</i> =						37	8
	Kappa		Interpretation*				
Facilitating Factors	1		Perfect Agreement				
Hindering Factors	0.16		Slight Agreement				

*<0.00 Poor Agreement 0.00-0.20 Slight Agreement 0.21-0.40 Fair Agreement 0.41-0.60 Moderate Agreement 0.61-0.80 Substantial Agreement 0.81-1.00 Perfect Agreement

Meanwhile, the content validity of the instrument was determined through the Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio (CVR) to assure whether it measures the content area it is expected to measure. It involves a panel of experts rating items as either essential, useful, but not essential, or not essential. Items rated as essential by a critical number of panel members

are included in the final instrument, while items rated otherwise were discarded (Ayre & Scally, 2014). Table 2 shows the rating of ten (10) validators on the given items under two (2) categories, namely (a) Facilitating Factors in Implementation of School Programs and (b) Hindering Factors in Implementation of School Programs.

Table 2 Content Validity Ratio of Items Under the Category of Facilitating Factors in the Implementation of School Programs

Facilitating Factors	Rating			CVR	Interpretation*
	Useful	Useful But Not Essential	Not Essential		
Collaboration and harmonious relationship among teaching and non-teaching personnel	10	0	0	1	R
Effective leadership and monitoring by the school head	10	0	0	1	R
Teachers' high commitment and dedication	10	0	0	1	R
Stakeholders' active involvement, responsibility, and accountability	10	0	0	1	R
Open, constant, and transparent communication channels	10	0	0	1	R
Alignment and adaptability of the program to the school's context and needs	10	0	0	1	R
Provision of technical assistance by division personnel	10	0	0	1	R
Utilization of research-based and data-driven practices	10	0	0	1	R
Integration of technology across various aspects of program implementation	10	0	0	1	R
Hindering Factors	Rating			CVR	Interpretation*
	Useful	Useful But Not Essential	Not Essential		
Unforeseen weather /calamity disturbances resulting to changes in learning modalities	7	3	0	0.4	E
Implementation of the "No Disruption of Classes" policy	8	0	2	0.6	R
Requires sufficient funding, materials, technology, and space in the school premises	8	0	2	0.6	R
Lack of understanding on program implementation, monitoring, and evaluation	10	0	0	1	R
Low commitment and dedication of teachers	10	0	0	1	R
Low stakeholders' support	10	0	0	1	R
Numerous teacher workloads and lack of manpower	8	0	2	0.6	R
Poor coordination between teaching and non-teaching personnel	10	0	0	1	R

Time constraints and conflicting schedule of activities	10	0	0	1	R
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*R = Retain and E = Eliminate

Based on the results of the content validation, the item “unforeseen weather/calamity disturbances resulting to changes in learning modalities” under the category of hindering factors was recommended to be eliminated. To balance the number of items in each category, the researcher decided to omit the item “integration of technology across various aspects of program implementation” under the category of Facilitating Factors. Survey items were further calibrated based on the comments and suggestions of validators before their transmission to the online survey application.

4.3. Data Analysis

This study analyzed data in the demographic profile of the respondents using frequency and percentages. Rank analysis was used for the general rank of facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation of school programs. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare the differences in rankings of facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation of school programs when respondents are grouped according to their profile.

5. Discussion of Results and Recommendations

This section contains the presentation and analysis of data gathered from the survey instrument administered to the participants. The order of discussion is based on the research questions study.

5.1. Research Question No. 1:

- What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Sex (Male or Female)
 - Number of Years Serving as School Head
 - Educational Attainment
 - Level of School Handled (Elementary, Junior High School, Senior High School)

Table 3 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. Twenty-six percent (26%) of the respondents are male, while seventy-four percent (74%) are female. The dominance in the number of female school heads supports the claim of Varghese & Selvasundaram (2024) on the feminization of the teaching profession, which characterizes the significant presence of females in the field of education. On the other hand, thirty-seven percent (37%) of the respondents served five years or shorter as a school head, while nineteen percent (19%) served between six and ten years, and forty-four percent (44%) served for eleven years or longer. This signifies that the majority of the respondents are considered elderly leaders, which may be exemplified as those with more knowledge and skills in making sound and excellent decisions because of their wide experience in the field (Fresh Essays, 2022). In terms of educational attainment, thirty-three percent (33%) of the respondents have obtained units in a master’s degree, while twelve percent (12%) have completed their master’s degree. Twenty-three percent (23%) have obtained units in doctorate degree, while thirty-two percent (32%) have completed their doctorate degree. From these results, it could be gleaned that the respondents are involved with continuous professional development as a way to increase the likelihood of exhibiting the democratic leadership style in schools (Kotur & Anbazhagan, 2014). Further, sixty-five percent (65%) of the respondents manage public elementary schools, while twenty-three percent (23%) manage public high schools, and twelve percent (12%) manage public senior high schools. This signifies that public elementary schools are more prevalent in the community. Since the number of public junior high and senior high schools does not counterbalance with the number of elementary schools, learners tend to transfer to private institutions in their higher levels of basic education. Unfortunately, learners with lower socioeconomic status are forced to enroll in public junior high and senior high schools, resulting in overcrowding of learners in classrooms and campuses.

Table 3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Sex	Male	11
	Female	32
Number of Years Serving as School Head	5 years and below	16
	6-10 years	8

	11 years and above	19
Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	0
	With Master's Degree Units	14
	With Complete Master's Degree	5
	With Doctorate Degree Units	10
	With Complete Doctorate Degree	14
Level of School Handled	Elementary	28
	Junior High	10
	Senior High	5

5.2. Research Question No. 2

How do respondents rank the given facilitating and hindering factors in terms of contribution to the implementation of school programs?

Survey results show that the respondents consider the alignment and adaptability of the program to the school's context and needs as the most contributory facilitating factor in the successful implementation of school programs. This adheres to the assertion of Silmere, Raghavan, Hovmand, Aarons, Bungler, & Hensley (2011) that program implementation outcomes may be measured by the program's appropriateness, relevance, and compatibility to a certain context. Meanwhile, the effective leadership and monitoring by the school head is perceived subsequently as a contributory facilitating factor in the successful implementation of school programs. This adheres with the claim of Chatzipanagiotou & Katsarou (2023) that school leaders are responsible for the proper planning, implementation, monitoring, and review of school programs to ensure their contribution to overall school effectiveness. On the other hand, the utilization of research-based and data-driven practices was seen by the respondents as a strategy and intervention for concerns in school management, as likewise declared by Libdan, Robles, & Rollo (2023). This result is in coherence with the statement of Durlak (2013) that conducting the application of scientific theory and research is a leading contributory factor affecting program implementation. To add, Fullan (2011) supports the notion that collaboration and harmonious relationships among teaching and non-teaching personnel encourage group effort, resulting in a positive leverage on the implementation of school programs.

In terms of the provision of technical assistance, Fullan (2011) stated that capacity-building, group work, and instruction given by personnel from the higher offices may enhance continuous improvement of school programs since it focuses on inspiring positive change in school systems. Emerging as six on the list of facilitating factors contributing to the successful implementation of school programs is teachers' high commitment and dedication. Hallinger & Heck (2011) affirmed that the involvement of teachers in school programs is crucial, as they are the curriculum implementers directly affecting learners' attainment of academic outcomes. Fullan (2011) also stated that making sure that decision-makers, school heads, and teaching and non-teaching personnel communicate expectations, goals, and the value of a program in a clear, succinct, and timely manner can guarantee that everyone is on the same page and working toward the same goals. On top of that, stakeholders' active involvement, responsibility, and accountability enhances school programs as it offers opportunities to offer full engagement in meeting learner needs.

Table 4 General Rank of Facilitating Factors in Terms of Contribution to Successful Implementation of School Programs

	Rank
Alignment and adaptability of the program to the school's context and needs	1
Effective leadership and monitoring by the school head	2
Utilization of research-based and data-driven practices	3
Collaboration and harmonious relationship among teaching and non-teaching personnel	4
Provision of technical assistance by division personnel	5
Teachers' high commitment and dedication	6

Open, constant, and transparent communication channels	7
Stakeholders' active involvement, responsibility, and accountability	8

When it comes to the hindering factors contributing to the unsuccessful implementation of school programs, survey results show that the respondents consider time constraints and a conflicting schedule of activities as the ultimate reason for the failure to execute plans in the realization of school programs. DepEd Order No. 5, Series of 2024, entitled Rationalization of Teachers' Workload in Public Schools and Payment of Teaching Overload stipulates that teachers shall render six hours of actual classroom teaching and two hours of teaching-related duties daily. Due to different forms of preparation for actual classroom teaching, teachers usually find it difficult to fulfill their tasks related to the implementation of school programs. Some teachers even consider school programs as a burden instead of realizing their worth in the improvement of learners' academic outcomes. Survey results also show that the respondents ranked poor coordination between teaching and non-teaching personnel as a second-topmost contributory factor to the unsuccessful implementation of school programs. Fullan (2011) discussed that coordinating the program's objectives with internal and external stakeholders drives success at a task that is meaningful and contributes to the wellness of others. Guskey & Yoon (2009) added teachers must understand the aims and objectives of school programs as well as how it fits within the curriculum. Teachers interact with information, communicate with numerous entities, confer with them, and engage in negotiation as part of carrying out additional duties in relation to the implementation of school programs. Further, the low commitment and dedication of teachers is seen by the respondents as the second eminent factor in the unsuccessful implementation of school programs. Palestina, Pangan, and Ancho (2020) asserted that teachers' commitment serves as an essential factor in successful program implementation. An important measure of how well a school is managed is how involved its teachers are in its operations. Only when teachers engage in long-term, constructive, and continuous participation will the school's institutional goals be achieved.

On top of that, Carillo & Janer (2022) proclaimed that school programs will be better implemented when working conditions of teachers are improved. The biggest challenges that teachers encounter when taking part in school programs are the abundance of paperwork, longer working hours, lack of opportunities for teachers to showcase their abilities, and a lack of support for creating an environment that fosters learning. Moreover, school heads often expect teachers to handle a variety of organizational and administrative tasks. Next, the implementation of the "No Disruption of Classes" policy through DepEd Order No. 9 series of 2005 hampered the implementation of school programs as it requires the maximization of time allotment for each learning area and lessening of activities that interfere with regular classroom work. Fullan (2011) added that community support enhances activities that require all stakeholders to offer full engagement in meeting learner needs. Stakeholders may offer help in forms of finances and manpower. Epstein (2011) reiterated that parents, as members of the educational community, may also aid in the successful implementation of school programs as they can provide valuable insights and feedback on the program's implementation. In relation to this, Henderson & Mapp (2002) stated that when parents are involved in the implementation of school programs, learners' motivation and academic performance are enhanced. Generally, Durlak (2013) concluded that many stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, local practitioners, and local administrators, are jointly responsible for high-quality implementation of school programs. The better the implementation, the more likely it is that the program will provide the desired results. On the other hand, Fullan (2011) avowed that adequate funding is crucial for the successful implementation of school programs. It ensures that resources are available to support the program's implementation, including training materials and equipment. Moreover, Durlak (2013) listed adequate funding as a societal factor that influences the quality of the implementation process. School programs in the Philippines are funded by the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) as stipulated in DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2009. The MOOE shall be used to fund activities listed in the approved School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Plan (AIP). It may also be utilized for the procurement of supplies and consumables for learners and personnel, as well as the minor repair of tools and equipment in the school, as long as it is included in the SIP and AIP.

Table 5 General Rank of Hindering Factors in Terms of Contribution to Unsuccessful Implementation of School Programs

	Rank
Time constraints and conflicting schedule of activities	1
Poor coordination between teaching and non-teaching personnel	2
Lack of understanding on program implementation, monitoring, and evaluation	3

Low commitment and dedication of teachers	4
Numerous teacher workloads and lack of manpower	5
Implementation of the “No Disruption of Classes” policy	6
Low stakeholders’ support	7
Requires sufficient funding, materials, technology, and space in the school premises	8

5.3. Research Question No. 3

How do perceptions on facilitating and hindering factors differ when grouped according to respondents’ profile?

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to examine the differences between the ranks of facilitating and hindering factors in terms of their contribution to the implementation of school programs according to multiple groups of participants, such as sex, number of years serving as school head, educational attainment, and level of school handled. As seen on the following table, no significant differences were observed on the perceptions of respondents on facilitating factors on the successful implementation of school programs when grouped according to sex with rank totals of (A) 68.5 and (B) 67.5, where $H=0.0028$, $df=1$, $p=3.84$, number of years serving as school head with rank totals of (A) 100, (B) 99.5, and (C) 100.5, where $H=0.0012$, $df=2$, $p=5.99$, educational attainment with rank totals of (A) 132, (B) 132, (C) 132.5, and (D) 131.5, where $H=0.0007$, $df=3$, $p=7.81$, and level of school handled with rank totals of (A) 106.5, (B) 97, and (C) 96.5, where $H=0.1587$, $df=2$, $p=5.99$.

Table 6 Rank of Facilitating Factors in Terms of Contribution to Successful Implementation of School Programs According to Demographic Profile

	Sex		Number of Years Serving as School Head			Educational Attainment				Level of School Handled		
	Male	Female	5 years and below	6-10 years	11 years and above	With Master’ s Degree Units	With Complete Master’ s Degree	With Doctorate Degree Units	With Complete Doctorate Degree	Elementary	Junior High	Senior High
	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(A)	(B)	(C)
Collaboration and harmonious relationship among teaching and non-teaching personnel	2	4	5	8	3.5	5	3	3	4	3	6	3
Effective leadership and monitoring by the school head	5.5	1	3	2	3.5	1	1	5	1	2	5	1
Teachers’ high commitment and dedication	3.5	6.5	8	6	3.5	4	4	4	2.5	4	8	4

Stakeholders' active involvement, responsibility, and accountability	5.5	8	7	6	3.5	8	7.5	1.5	8	8	7	7.5
Open, constant, and transparent communication channels	7	5	6	3	7	7	5	1.5	7	6	4	5
Alignment and adaptability of the program to the school's context and needs	1	2	2	4	1	3	2	7	5	1	1.5	2
Provision of technical assistance by division personnel	3.5	6.5	4	1	8	6	7.5	8	6	7	3	7.5
Utilization of research-based and data-driven practices	8	3	1	6	6	2	6	6	2.5	8	1.5	6
Mean Rank	68.5	67.5	100	99.5	100.5	132	132	132.5	131.5	106.5	97	96.5
Kruskal-Wallis H	0.0028		0.0012			0.0007				0.1587		
Df	1		2			3				2		
Asymp.Sig. p	3.84		5.99			7.81				5.99		

Similarly, no significant differences were observed on the perceptions of respondents on hindering factors on the unsuccessful implementation of school programs when grouped according to sex with rank totals of (A) 68 and (B) 68, where $H=0$, $df=1$, $p=3.84$, number of years serving as school head with rank totals of (A) 100, (B) 100.5, and (C) 99.5, where $H=0.0012$, $df=2$, $p=5.99$, educational attainment with rank totals of (A) 133, (B) 133, (C) 130.5, and (D) 131.5, where $H=0.0064$, $df=3$, $p=7.81$, and level of school handled with rank totals of (A) 99, (B) 102, and (C) 99, where $H=0.1587$, $df=2$, $p=5.99$.

Table 7 Rank of Hindering Factors in Terms of Contribution to Unsuccessful Implementation of School Programs According to Demographic Profile

	Sex		Number of Years Serving as School Head			Educational Attainment				Level of School Handled		
	Male	Female	5 years and below	6-10 years	11 years and above	With master's Degree Units	With Complete Master's Degree	With Doctorate Degree Units	With Complete Doctorate Degree	Elementary	Junior High	Senior High
	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(A)	(B)	(C)

Implementation of the “No Disruption of Classes” policy	1	5	8	5	6	3.5	3	5	3	3	8	3
Requires sufficient funding, materials, technology, and space in the school premises	8	4	5	1	2	7.5	1	6	7.5	8	5	1
Lack of understanding on program implementation, monitoring, and evaluation	4.5	3	7	6.5	7.5	7.5	4	8	7.5	6	3	4
Low commitment and dedication of teachers	6	6.5	1.5	8	4.5	2	6.5	1	2	4.5	7	6.5
Low stakeholders’ support	2	8	3	2	3	6	5	3	6	7	6	5
Numerous teacher workloads and lack of manpower	7	2	6	6.5	1	3.5	2	7	4	2	4	2
Poor coordination between teaching and non-teaching personnel	4.5	6.5	4	3	7.5	5	6.5	3	5	4.5	3	6.5
Time constraints and conflicting schedule of activities	3	1	1.5	4	4.5	1	8	3	1	1	1	8
Mean Rank	68	68	100	100.5	99.5	133	133	130.5	131.5	99	102	99
Kruskal-Wallis H	0		0.0012			0.0064				0.1587		
Df	1		2			3				2		
Asymp.Sig. p	3.84		5.99			7.81				5.99		

A post-hoc test was not administered since no differences between the groups were observed. With the abovementioned results, a technical assistance plan for school heads will be developed based on the general rank of facilitating and hindering factors in terms of contribution to the successful or unsuccessful implementation of school programs.

5.4. Research Question No. 4

What technical assistance plan for school heads can be developed based on the findings?

Merely evaluating program impact without knowing how well a program was executed can produce unreliable results. A more comprehensive understanding of their programs and a better capacity to recognize and share exemplary practices can be gained by educators through the effective evaluation of their impacts. A program's relationship to observed outcomes can be interpreted more precisely if it is known whether it was effectively implemented. Without a good knowledge of these concerns, educators may have trouble repeating previously successful programs because they won't know how to do it with the necessary integrity to achieve the desired results (Duerden & Witt, 2012). To ensure successful implementation of school programs in the City Schools Division of Bacoor, the following technical assistance plan is proposed:

Table 8 Technical assistance plan Fiscal Year 2025

Priority Need for Improvement: Time Management				
Objectives	Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Resources
Strengthen time management strategies for the prioritization of activities	1. Conduct capacity building on time management principles and strategies	January 2025	School heads, Facilitators	Budget for capacity building Training materials
	2. Conduct workshops on the development of action plans for school programs	January 2025	School heads, Facilitators	Budget for workshop Workshop materials
	3. Conduct individual coaching sessions through field visits to tailor strategies to individual school needs	Throughout the year	School heads, Parent supervisors	None
Priority Need for Improvement: Personnel Management				
Foster collaborative work environment in schools	1. Conduct seminars on effective personnel management practices	January 2025	School heads, Facilitators	Budget for capacity building Training materials
Priority Need for Improvement: Strategies for Planning, Implementation, Monitoring and Evaluation of Programs				
Implement all planned school programs with positive results for beneficiaries	1. Conduct capacity building on program planning, monitoring, and evaluation	January 2025	School heads, Facilitators	Budget for capacity building Training materials
	2. Conduct individual coaching sessions through field visits to provide technical assistance on the implementation of school programs	Throughout the year	School heads, Parent supervisors	None
	3. Conduct benchmarking of best practices in the implementation of school programs	November 2025	School heads, Parent supervisors	None
Priority Need for Improvement: Additional Manpower				
Establish wider support systems in schools for the implementation of school programs	1. Coordinating with the local government unit for the recruitment of additional non-teaching personnel	January 2025	Personnel Unit	Budget for salaries of additional non-teaching personnel

	2. Requesting for additional non-teaching personnel items from higher offices	January 2025	Personnel Unit	Budget for salaries of additional non-teaching personnel
Priority Need for Improvement: Stakeholder Partnership				
Promote shared goals with internal and external stakeholders in schools	1. Conduct capacity building on strengthening stakeholder partnerships	January 2025	School heads, Facilitators	Budget for capacity building Training materials
	2. Conduct individual coaching sessions through field visits to provide technical assistance on strengthening stakeholder partnerships	Throughout the year	School heads, Parent supervisors	None
	3. Conduct benchmarking of best practices in stakeholder partnerships	November 2025	School heads, Parent supervisors	None
	4. Provide tools and guidelines for developing stakeholder partnerships.	January 2025	Social Mobilization and Networking Unit	None

This Technical Assistance Plan aims to address the prioritized needs of school heads by providing structured activities, utilizing expert resources, and setting clear timeframes to ensure effective outcomes. The plan includes workshops, training sessions, individual coaching, and the development of tools and resources to enhance skills in time management, personnel management, program planning, manpower needs, and stakeholder partnerships.

After the results of the quantitative instruments were analyzed and interpreted, this study therefore makes the following conclusions:

- School heads, together with other internal and external stakeholders, play an important role in the successful implementation of school programs.
- Alignment and adaptability of programs to the school's context is perceived as the leading contributory factor in the successful implementation of school programs.
- Time constraints and conflict of schedules are perceived as the leading contributory factors in the unsuccessful implementation of school programs.
- Factors such as sex, number of years serving as school head, educational attainment, and level of school handled have no influence on how the implementation of school programs may be perceived.

6. Conclusion

Given the conclusions presented, this study presents the following recommendations to ensure successful implementation of school programs:

- School programs must be strictly supervised from the stages of planning, implementation, and review.
- In the planning phase, alignment and adaptability of programs to the school's context must be given utmost priority since it is considered a major contributory factor in the successful implementation of school programs.

- Plotting of annual school activities must be aligned with the calendar of activities in the Department of Education Central, Regional, and Division offices to minimize unsuccessful implementation of school programs caused by time constraints and conflicting schedules.
- The proposed Technical Assistance Plan for school heads may be utilized in the City Schools Division of Bacoor.
- Further research should be done in other school divisions and private schools to compare the facilitating and hindering factors in the implementation of school programs.

Compliance with ethical standards

The study guarantees adherence to research ethics set by the Department of Education. The respondents' involvement in the online survey will have no negative or positive effects. The researchers listed potential advantages, such as the publishing of the research findings. The respondents were ensured anonymity since their names and other personal details were not sought in the poll. The respondents' profiles were only utilized for the study's analysis and interpretation. In addition, it was made clear to the respondents that they are under no obligation to complete the survey and might stop at any point if they so desired.

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